

Identification of Phenols on the Basis of Absorption Maxima of Coloured Products Formed in the Ag^+ Catalysed Oxidation by Peroxydisulphate

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A scheme for the identification of 26 phenols has been proposed. This is based on the reaction of aqueous peroxydisulphate solution with the phenols (in 50% acetone-water solution) in presence of Ag^+ as catalyst, resulting in the formation of differently coloured solutions (in most cases) with differing absorption-maxima in the visible range. Microgram amounts of phenols can be detected and identified by this method.

THE oxidation of phenols by peroxydisulphate ion in alkaline medium has been studied¹⁻⁴. The reaction products are coloured^{5,6} and a number of products are formed. Recently, following the preliminary work of Khulbe and Srivastava⁷ on the colour changes observed during the oxidation of different phenols by $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ in aqueous medium, Srivastava and coworkers⁸⁻¹⁰ carried out the kinetic study of Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of phenols in acetone-water medium. During the systematic study of the Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of different phenols by peroxydisulphate ion in acetone-water medium, it was observed that the phenols generally give differently coloured products which remain in solution for a considerably long time (after which precipitation of the product starts) and show absorption maxima at different wavelengths in the visible range. It is thus possible that these reactions, under suitable conditions, may be used as a method for identification of various phenols on the basis of the colour of the reaction products and their absorption maxima observed before the precipitation starts. With this end in view, the absorption maxima of the coloured solutions formed by the addition of potassium peroxydisulphate to solutions of different phenols in acetone-water medium in presence of 0.01% aqueous AgNO_3 were studied and on the basis of the study, a suitable scheme for identification of this class of compounds is proposed.

Experimental

Chemicals: Potassium peroxydisulphate and silver nitrate (G.R., E. Merck) were used after recrystallisation. Acetone (B.D.H., AnalaR) was distilled before use. Various phenols of B.D.H., E. Merck, Riedel, Fluka, Aldrich or Koch-Light grade were used after recrystallisation or redistillation.

Procedure: To 5 ml of 0.4-0.5% (v/v) solution of

phenols in 50% acetone was added 5 ml of 1% aqueous solution of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ and 1 ml of 0.01% aqueous AgNO_3 . The test tubes were allowed to stand at room temperature for about 10-15 min, when colour developed. The absorption maxima were determined by 'Spectronic 20' spectrophotometer before the precipitation started in the reaction mixture.

The colour change in the solutions and the observed absorption maxima in the Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of various phenols are tabulated in Table 1, where the detection limit for various phenols are also recorded.

It is important to point out here that the λ_{max} did not change during the entire period of reaction before precipitation started and that the absorbance values did not change significantly at the position of the maximum.

Scheme for identification: On the basis of the above observation, the following scheme for identification of various closely related phenols is proposed.

To 5 ml solution (about 0.4-0.5% by volume) of phenol in 50% acetone are added 5 ml 1% aqueous solution of potassium peroxydisulphate and 1 ml 0.01% aqueous solution of AgNO_3 . The mixture is allowed to stand for 15 min and position of λ_{max} is noted. The Table 1, which records the colour of the reaction product in the solution and the corresponding absorption maxima, for various phenols can be used to identify the phenols.

It is worthwhile to point out here that the phenols could not be identified in presence of aromatic amines or another phenol.

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TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Name of the compound	b.p./m.p. ^a	Colour of the reaction product in solution	Absorption maximum (λ_{max}) nm	Detection limit (μ g)
1.	Phenol	40 ^s	Violet	400	50
2.	<i>o</i> -Cresol	32 ^s	Brown	405	60
3.	<i>m</i> -Cresol	203	Light brown	400	65
4.	<i>p</i> -Cresol ^b	36 ^s	Blackish yellow	360	70
5.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol	175	Yellowish	410	55
6.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenol	33 ^s	Brown	325	60
7.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	44 ^s	Violet	335	70
8.	<i>o</i> -Bromophenol	195	Brown	410	75
9.	Catechol	105 ^s	Greenish	395	20
10.	Resorcinol ^b	110 ^s	Light brown	360	25
11.	Quinol	237 ^s	Black	410	30
12.	Salicylaldehyde	197	Yellow	430	75
13.	<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenol ^b	159 ^s	Reddish orange	350	60
14.	<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenol ^b	202 ^s	Yellowish orange	410	70
15.	<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenol	214 ^s	Yellowish	330	80
16.	<i>o</i> -Phenylphenol ^b	56 ^s	Yellow	350	70
17.	<i>p</i> -Phenylphenol	166 ^s	Dark yellow	420	75
18.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenol	205	Yellow	475	50
19.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenol	53 ^s	Yellowish pink	370	50
20.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	45 ^s	Yellow	340	75
21.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenol	96 ^s	Light yellow	360	75
22.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	114 ^s	Dark yellow	380	80
23.	<i>o</i> -Aminophenol	110 ^s	Yellowish orange	410	20
24.	<i>m</i> -Aminophenol	122 ^s	Dirty yellow	450	20
25.	<i>p</i> -Aminophenol	184 ^s	Violet	510	20
26.	Pyrogallol	133 ^s	Dark brown	480	10

a - The values of m.p./b.p. are taken from 'Hand Book of Chemistry and Physics', (Ed.) Charles D. Hodgman.

b - Absorption maximum is broad, s - Solid.

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